

Fuzzy correlation similarity measurement of color-histograms

Abstract

Fuzzy correlation of color-histograms is proposed for measure the similarity between the color images. A weighted algorithm was demonstrated of calculating the peak value of the correlation, it shows the flexibility to search to an image and its best matching images with color distortion and color characters. Experimental examples show the effectiveness of this method in retrieving of color images of specific color content.

Keywords: color histogram; Pattern recognition

1. Introduction

One of Color-histograms powerful applications is the color-content based image matching, among which content- based image retrieval (CBIR) has been a major to- pic of research for the last few years [3]. As a crude approximation to CBIR. the first approach was proposed where peaks in the color-histograms were matched using only color similarity measures in the color-space based on the concepts of fuzzy set theory [4].

In addition to setting constraints on the color similarity between histogram peaks, in this report, a concept of correlation to color-image histograms is introduced for the similarity measures between histograms before making the decision to match them or not. Moreover, flexibility is introduced by defining colors of interest through a set of weights in the similarity measure. Two alternatives to selecting the weights are proposed. The first extension is to assign matched histogram peaks a weight proportional to their height, thereby giving more importance in the similarity measure process to the largest image segments: in the following, this is termed the “uniform weight” approach. A more elaborate idea is to empirically define a set of weights to highlight those peaks that are considered of most importance for the task at hand, thus optimizing the similarity measure operation based on some selected features: this is called the “non uniform weight” approach and can be understood as one form of artificial color manipulation of images [5]. Diverse experimental results show that the proposed algorithm can be effectively employed for retrieval purposes, especially for the retrieval of color images with color aberrations or with local features of interest.

2. Fuzzy measure to color-histograms

A normalized color-histogram can be considered as a transformation of a color image and a similarity measure between two color-histograms can be used for color-content-based similarity measure of images. The interest of using color-histograms is comforted by the following evidence that we gathered

from our numerical experiments: in a complex environment involving many image segments with color textures, color contents similarity is a particularly robust signature of the similarity between scenes. Therefore, histograms can be employed as criteria to retrieve color images, with a high success rate.

To perform color image comparison based on color statistics, firstly a histogram is computed from the color image data. In practice, this may start from the RGB space, which is an “artificial color” space as stressed in [5] and is supposed to mimic hu-man vision in a fair way considering its simplicity. In fact, many image sensors, in particular CCD cameras, digitize images on approximations of the RGB space but other spaces could be used as well. Nevertheless, keeping in mind that our goal in this study is to mimic human observer performance, we expect that the RGB space as approximated by a CCD camera is at least a good first approximation. The numerical experiments reported on throughout this work are based on this assumption.

2.1. Histogram building

The color-histogram is a descriptor of the number of image or region pixels of a specified color in a color image. Specifically, it is defined as:

$$\langle C, M, \{\delta Ci\}, \{H(\delta Ci)\} \rangle$$

where C is a chosen color space, δCi is the color quantization cell i , $i = 1$ through M, M is the number of color cells and by the same token the number of histogram “peaks”, $H(\delta Ci) = N_i/N$, N_i is the number of image pixels whose color falls in the color space cell (or “bin”) δCi and N is the total number of image pixels.

In the specific case of the examples below, a commercial minimum variance quantization soft- ware tool [6] was used to automatically determine the color space bins, thus defining sensible histograms and yet using a relatively small number M of cells. In short, the 3-D color space is partitioned into M compact bins δCi (not necessarily cubes) of different sizes, and bins are smaller in those regions of the color space that occur most frequently. Of course, each histogram peak is therefore associated to the description of its “bin” shape, but its first attribute is its bin center of gravity.

Once histograms have been computed for the images to be compared with the same M value, they are labeled according to their height: each histogram therefore consists of peak height values h_l , $l=1$ to M, with for all l $h_l \geq h_{l+1}$. Then, a comparison between histograms can be then carried out based on their peak matching both in their color distance and in their height.

2.2. Height-matching of histogram peaks

In a second selection step, all retained color- matched peaks are examined and their fuzzy similarity is expressed by the following membership function as:

$$R = \sum_{i=1}^M H\mu(t, t')_s$$

where H is a weighted factor proportional to the color and height matched pixel-numbers or area, $\mu(t, t')$ and the weight $\mu = 1$ correspondent to “uniform weight algorithm”, while weight bl of an empirically selected value to “non-uniform weight algorithm” for some special case, as will be illustrated in the examples below.

In the defuzzification of the membership function of histogram similarity with the threshold value a_3 , R_h will be valued with 1 or 0, to declare a histogram-matching or not, respectively.

3. Experiment of image retrieval

In this set of experiments, 9000 pieces of color images of themes of landscapes were downloaded from a public image database, with which a database was constructed for the experimental sampling with no modulation of their original resolutions. Because the similarity measure is based on the color-histograms, instead of the correspondent color where primed quantities refer to a given image and non-primed quantities, to the image to be compared.

In the next step, peak value, R, of the fuzzy correlation function for the two discrete curves, namely the two peak distributions in the two color-histograms, can be calculated as the membership function of histogram similarity images, and all the images are stored in fact in the database in the form of their normalized histograms with 16 peaks ($M = 16$, for practice) transformed by the software MATLAB automatically in the pre-process. The type of images is JPEG or GIF in RGB color-space. Colors units in all three dimensions were normalized, such that all r, g and b values are between 0 and 1.

In the experiments, unless otherwise specified, one image from the base is selected at random to serve as the query image. The full base is then screened for matches and the number of index images matched to some specified degree is determined. All the retrieved images are subjectively examined like the query image and the statistic results show that less and less images with an increased similarity can be retrieved along with the increase of the threshold values controlling the precision of the similarity measure, see Figs. 1, for the example of a_3 and a_1 , respectively. Of course, in all these cases the query image itself is recognized for the most sensible value of the parameters.

Fig. 1. Retrieval experiment result by uniform weight approach, (image resolution: $145 \cdot 109$, $a_1 = 0.94$, $a_2 = 0.9$). (a) Query image and the only retrieved image with $a_3 = 0.5625$. (a)–(c) Three retrieved images with $a_3 = 0.5$. (a)–(f) Six retrieved images with $a_3 = 0.4375$.

Given a database of RGB image, this method therefore involves three parameters, a_1 , a_2 and a_3 . These parameters are empirically determined by the user on a training set for each given recognition task and data base. Once the parameters have been empirically optimized, the procedure can run automatically. The criteria of the training results of the retrieval will be evaluated eventually based on the human perception. Further study to complement the present work could involve optimizing the parameters automatically, either in a supervised mode where the user defines the goals in terms of image matching on a set of query images – index image pairs, or even in an unsupervised mode.

4. Discussion and conclusions

A specific fuzzy correlation process for similarity measure of color-histograms and a weight algorithm in the fuzzy correlation was defined. The uniformly weighted fuzzy correlation applied to color image retrieval, controlled by the pre-defined parameters was demonstrated. Based on the technology introduced in the paper, retrieval is achieved straight forwardly, and images are closely matched to their counterparts in the search image, in the uniform weight algorithm. The weight algorithm in the fuzzy correlation is always possible to carry out the retrievals of different pictures databases.

References

- [1] M.J. Swain, D.H. Ballard, *Int. J. Comput. Vision* 7 (1991) 11.
- [2] B.M. Mehre, M.S. Kankanhalli, A.D. Narasimhalu et al., *Pattern Recogn. Lett.* 16 (1995) 325.
- [3] A. del Bimbo, *Visual Information Retrieval*, Morgan Kaufmann Inc, San Francisco, 1999.
- [4] L.A. Zadeh, *Inform. Control* 8 (1965) 338.
- [5] J. Fu, H.J. Caulfield, S.R. Pulusani, *J. Electron. Imaging* 13 (2004) 553.
- [6] Matlab, *Image Processing Toolbox User's Guide*, Version 2, The Mathworks Inc., p. 196.